

Conquering barriers to healthcare in Rajpur, rural Nepal

Can access to healthcare be achieved despite geographical challenges?
A geospatial analysis of the problem and policy recommendations.

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Rajpur, rural Nepal

Rajpur Rural Municipality is a municipality in southwestern Nepal with a population of about 28,000 spread out over an area of 577 square kilometers.

Slightly over half of the population lives in the narrow river plain, and the rest live in scattered settlements in the mountainous south.

There are no paved roads in most of the mountainous region - making it extremely difficult for transportation. The elderly, sick, and pregnant women are especially at risk in case of emergencies.

Villagers take a trail from a village in the southern mountains towards the municipal center, where markets and roads are.

Access to Rajpur Healthcare Center is limited by distance and natural barriers like mountains and roads without bridges.

Each settlement in Rajpur Rural Municipality color-coded by its distance from Rajpur Health Center, the main municipal health center.

In some villages of Rajpur, access to even the most basic healthcare services can be a challenge, with travel times to the nearest health facility exceeding seven hours.

Risky pregnancies

Women are disproportionately impacted by challenging terrain - even more so if they need to seek reproductive healthcare. Most maternal deaths occur in the post-partum period, right after birth - a sensitive time for the life of the pregnant woman and the newborn. Distance and lack of preparedness can be dangerous.

Only a few settlements have access to birthing centers during the rainy season. A large segment of the population does not have access to safe childbirth.

During the rainy season, access is further compromised by poor roads. In Rajpur, the areas with the highest distances to birthing centers are also the areas with the highest maternal deaths or unaddressed complications.

Program and Policy Design

Given these challenges, the municipality has partnered with Karma Health, a non-profit, to overcome some of these challenges. A study of the successes and failures of these approaches may provide insights into potential policy recommendations to tackle the problem of lack of access to healthcare in rural areas.

Pregnant women gather at an outreach camp where health providers bring ultrasound machines to remote villages.

1. Introduction of outreach health services that cater to those living in the remotest regions could be impactful. Specifically, targeting vulnerable groups like pregnant women and the elderly near their homes through mobile healthcare units may yield the most returns on investment.

Since pregnant women can not walk up and down the roadless hills for hours to reach the health centers, Karma Health conducts a mobile rural ultrasound program. Its clinicians walk and bike to remote villages on fixed dates each month to provide obstetric ultrasound care.

A medical doctor performs ultrasound scan of an pregnant woman in a outreach clinic that was 6 hours walk away from the health center.

2. Professional Community Health Workers can be an essential solution for addressing healthcare access issues. They not only provide basic testing and education but also act as facilitators for

Community health workers can work as health extenders and care coordinators to provide critical care and counseling.

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logistics, ensuring that individuals receive the care they need.

About this story

This article was produced by Bishal Belbase (MBBS, MPH) as a part of the coursework for the Master in Public Affairs degree at Princeton University taught by William Guthe and Tsering Shawa.

Images Karma Health, Author

Base Maps Esri, NASA, NGA, USGS,
Open Street Maps, Rajpur
Rural Municipality

Tools ArcGIS Pro, QGIS